

FILLING IN A GAP IN THE PROPERTY PROFILE OF GLASS COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT: This study describes the manufacturing and characterization of translucent glass matrix composites with enhanced fracture strength. An improvement of fracture toughness is realized by single (boron nitride) and double (boron nitride/titanium oxide) filament coatings, deposited by CVD. No significant influence of the coating technology on the fiber tensile strength was found. The composites, manufactured by hotpressing, have shown a fracture strength up to 320 MPa and an optical transmittance of about 10-13%. The interface regions were examined by AFM, SEM and TEM.

KEYWORDS: glass, composites, transmittance, fiber, coating

INTRODUCTION

Glass matrix composites have been investigated for many years with universal interest. The reinforcement of glass with different components like fibers, whiskers or platelets leads to an enhancement of fracture toughness, strength and thermoshock resistance compared to monolithic glass. In conjunction with useful glass properties like thermal stability and cost-effective availability these glass composites have widespread application possibilities. Some kinds have already been produced and sold on an industrial scale [1]. In the past there were undertaken some efforts to make glass composites transparent for the visible wavelength by adapting the optical properties of the components [2]. However, up to now a practical solution which meets the complex optical and mechanical claims has not been found. The improvement of fracture toughness by crack deflection, fiber debonding and fiber pull-out can only be achieved by a pure force- or shape-bonded fiber-matrix interface. The chemical interaction of the components leads to brittle fracture. Nevertheless optical transmittance requires the reduction of disturbing interfaces. The starting point for realizing good mechanical and optical composite properties is the adaption of the mechanical (YOUNG's modulus, thermal expansion) and optical (refractive index) properties of the components as well as a suitable interface between fiber and matrix provided by fiber coating. The fiber coating should meet the following requirements:

1. Optical transmittance in the visible wavelength
2. Prevent bonding of fiber and matrix by diffusion or reaction
3. Thermal and environmental resistance, also under oxidizing conditions

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With respect to the common coating concepts in fiber reinforced brittle matrix composites a non-oxidic boron nitride (BN) layer that has the same lubricious nature like pyrolytic carbon and an oxidic titania (TiO₂) layer were chosen, furthermore a boron nitride/titania double coating. Earlier investigations have proven the efficiency of double coating concepts [3,4].

EXPERIMENTAL

For the investigations presented here the following components were used (Table 1).

Table 1. Properties of the used composite components [5]

		Matrix glass 756f	Matrix glass N-SK4	Fiber Nextel 440
Manufactured by		TELUX	SCHOTT	3M
Refractive Index n_D		1,49	1,613	1,616
Thermal expansion coefficient (20..300°C)	[10 ⁻⁶ /K]	4,8	7,4	5,3
Transformation temperature	[°C]	500	658	-
YOUNG's-modulus	[GPa]	45	84	190
Bending strength	[MPa]	52	57	-
Tensile strength	[GPa]	-	-	2,07
Fiber diameter	[µm]	-	-	10-12
Filaments/Roving		-	-	750

CVD-coating of the Nextel 440 fiber with 40 or 100 nm boron nitride, 40 or 90 nm titania and the combination of these was carried out by continuous CVD under atmospheric pressure in a vertical hot-wall reactor. Before coating the fiber roving was thermally desized. The deposition of boron nitride was carried out by reaction of trimethoxyborane and ammonia. Analogously titania was received by thermal decomposition of tetraisopropyl orthotitanate in the presence of oxygen [6,7].

The fiber tensile strength tests and 3-point flexural strength tests were carried out with an INSTRON 4467, 10 N or, respectively, 2 kN load cell with respect to the procedures described in literature [8].

For scanning force microscopy (SFM) a TMX 2000 Explorer SPM from TopoMetrix was used. The measurement was carried out in the contact mode under atmospheric conditions.

The fiber rovings were infiltrated by a common slurry infiltration process (glass $d_{90} < 70\mu\text{m}$). All composites presented have an unidirectional fiber reinforcement. Composite manufacturing was done by hotpressing under the following conditions (figure 1):

Figure 1. Temperature-pressure-time-regime for making glass composites

The SEM imaging was performed with a CamScan 44 from Cambridge Instruments and a SEM XL 30 from FEI.

TEM investigations were carried out with a HITACHI H8010, 200 kV acceleration voltage. A part of the glass composite was sliced to 1 mm thickness, polished up to 5 μm grain size and ion polished with 3,5 keV Ar ions (GATAN PIPS).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. *Fiber and coating investigations*

The Nextel 440 fiber has a nanocrystalline structure and is specified to have 2070 MPa tensile strength. After thermal annealing at 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ mullit crystallisation was observed (XRD) [9]. For investigating the influence of the desizing and coating process on the mechanical fiber properties the fiber strength was determined by single fiber tensile test before and after annealing at elevated temperatures for 5 hours. The results are given in figure 2. Compared to the desized fiber no significant change in single fiber tensile strength was observed for both the single BN and TiO_2 coating, 40 and 100 (90) nm thickness respectively, as well as for the double coatings with different coating thickness up to 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Nevertheless both single coatings showed a decrease in tensile strength at 750 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ compared to all kinds of double coated fibers. It is established that the double coating process as well as the hotpressing process do not affect the tensile strength at lower temperatures in a significant manner. The double coating seems to combat fiber degradation in the investigated temperature area.

Figure 2. Results of single fiber tensile testing before and after annealing at elevated temperatures for 5 hours

As earlier reported the fiber roughness is important for toughening mechanisms in glass matrix composites [10]. The change of the fiber topography with increasing thermal annealing temperature (equal to the fiber tensile tests samples) was investigated by scanning force microscopy. Earlier investigations had shown a decrease of the surface roughness with increasing annealing temperature and coating thickness for the used boron nitride coated fibers [11]. For the desized fibers and fibers with titania single coating (25 and 100 nm) the particle size and surface roughness increased tendentiously with the annealing temperature. Similar results were found for the BN/TiO₂ double coatings. Figure 3 gives an impression of the fiber topography of a 35 nm BN/ 30 nm TiO₂ double coated Nextel 440 fiber before and after heat treatment at 750 °C.

Figure 3. AFM micrographs of 35 nm BN/30 nm TiO₂ coated Nextel 440 fiber “as received” (left) and after thermal annealing at 750 °C/5h (right)

SEM investigations (figure 4, left) proved a fine grained fiber surface after BN coating, similar to desized Nextel 440 fibers . The layer consists of turbostratic structure (TEM) [6]. The TiO₂ deposition gives a homogenous, crystalline and relatively dense layer (figure 4, right). Raman and XRD investigations proved an anatase structure which keeps unchanged at elevated temperatures [7].

Figure 4. SEM images of BN (left) coated Nextel 440 fiber surface and fracture mirror of a TiO₂ coated Nextel 440 fiber

2. *Composite characterization*

756f glass matrix

From the mechanical point of view borosilicate glass 756f matches well to the Nextel 440 fiber and it was often used in earlier investigations [9]. It was used for studying the interfacial properties and debonding behaviour and also with respect to the adaption of the refractive index in combination with other fibers. For studying the interfacial properties micromechanical “push in”- tests were performed [12]. The TiO₂ single layer has shown no debonding and, respectively, the BN single layer relatively high debonding forces. This happens because the fibers are strongly included in the glass matrix. Nevertheless the BN/TiO₂ double layer has shown a debonding behavior closely related to the well known pyrolytic carbon interfaces. The interfacial shear stress was found in the region of 50 MPa. The debonding mechanism was investigated by EDX analysis. Therefore the titania contents on the pull-out fibers and in the matrix channels were compared to that of “as received” double coated fibers. It seems very probable that the debonding occurs between the BN/TiO₂ interface. Selected results of the 3-point bending tests given in figure 5 are consistent with the micromechanical investigations. The fiber volume contents (FVC) were chosen as low as seen to combat fiber-fiber interactions during evaluating the coating systems and for comparability with the results with N-SK4 matrix glass presented below.

Figure 5. Bending curves of 756f glass/Nextel 440 fiber composites with different interphases

As expected the pure matrix glass and the composite with desized, uncoated fibers showed brittle fracture behaviour, similar to the titania interface composite (e.g. 40 nm/ FVC 10%: bending fracture strength 62 MPa, specific work of fracture 92 N/m). All of the boron nitride/titania double coatings have shown toughening by debonding and pull-out, even at relatively low fiber volume contents. Best results were obtained for the 40 nm BN/110 nm TiO₂ interface (specific work of fracture: 1900 N/m). The strength of these composites is about two times higher than that of the pure matrix glass. Earlier results have proven non-brittle fracture too for composites with boron nitride single layer but in a comparably smaller extent than that of the double layers (e.g. 40 nm BN/ FVC 12%: bending fracture strength 92 MPa, specific work of fracture 221 N/m) [13].

Figure 6 shows the pull-out region at the fracture surface of a 756f/Nextel 440 composite with the fiber/BN/TiO₂/matrix region in the composite (TEM) and the BN/TiO₂ interphase (SEM).

Figure 6. TEM image (left) of the interphases and SEM micrograph (right) of the fracture surface in 756f/BN/TiO₂/Nextel 440 composite

No conspicuous reaction zones between the interfaces were found in the TEM image. However, it is not safe to say that diffusions did not happen.

N-SK4 glass matrix

N-SK4 is an optical glass with a high barium oxide content. The intention was to improve the optical transmittance additional to the fiber reinforcement by adapted refractive index and reduced fiber volume content. The higher thermal expansion coefficient compared to the Nextel 440 fiber leads to thermal stress in the composite after cooling down and realizes a dense fiber-matrix transition for optical waveguidance. Equal to the 756f glass matrix the same coating systems on the Nextel 440 fiber were investigated in N-SK4-glass. As depicted in figure 7 the composites showed a completely different bending fracture behaviour than the 756f matrix composites.

Figure 7. Bending curves of N-SK4 glass/Nextel 440 fiber composites with different interphases

The pure matrix glass and the composites containing desized or titania coated fibers have shown brittle fracture. In some cases the chemical interaction of fibers and matrix lead to matrix micro cracks perpendicular to the fiber direction. Composites with boron nitride single coating and boron nitride/titania double coating showed an increased specific work of fracture up to 2000 N/m and bending fracture strength of more than 300 MPa. The values are similar to composites with pyrolytic carbon interphases, but in this case the FVC is not 15-17% but about 30-35% [9]. However, SEM micrograph investigations (figure 8) have proven effective toughening mechanisms but the final cracking is slight (40 nm BN-40 nm TiO₂), respectively, not delayed. This happens because of the high matrix-fiber clamp stress according to thermal expansion missmatch. It is assumed that the main reinforcement mechanism is energy dissipation by microcracking and crack deflection/delamination and, in a small extent debonding and pull-out.

Figure 8. Crack deflection/delamination (left) and pull-out in N-SK4/TiO₂/BN/Nextel 440 composites

The optical properties of the composites were investigated by the transmission spectra, given in figure 9.

Figure 9. Transmission spectra of N-SK4/Nextel 440 composites with different interphases, FVC \approx 15%

The samples with desized fibers and 40 nm TiO₂ interphase showed the best results, but as mentioned above brittle breaking was observed. However, the sample with 35 nm BN/ 30 nm TiO₂ coating is translucent and legibly improved mechanical properties were detected. For the boron nitride layers (40 nm) transmission was only 4%. In these cases a coating degradation in the course of technological steps might occur. Further investigations are necessary.

Figure 10 gives an imagination of the achieved translucency of different composites.

A

B

Figure 10. Optical micrographs of N-SK4/Nextel 440 composite samples with different interphases
A. 40 nm TiO₂ interphase
B. 35 nm BN/30 nm TiO₂ interphase

CONCLUSIONS

CVD-double fiber coatings of boron nitride and titania do not affect the single fiber tensile strength of Nextel 440 fibers in a significant manner. The titania coating seems to play a protective role toward the boron nitride coating during technological steps of the composite manufacturing. Double coatings have proven their ability to realize an improvement of the mechanical properties in glass matrix composites with unidirectional fiber reinforcement. The simultaneous retention of a partial transparency in the visible wavelength is possible by using optically adapted components. Debonding probably occurs between the two coatings investigated by EDX measurements of the titania content on broken samples. Beside fiber reinforcement microstresses realized by thermal expansion mismatch of fiber and matrix contribute to the good mechanical N-SK4/Nextel 440 composite properties and enable a lower fiber volume content for better optical transmittance.

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